

D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.1

Sample timeline by country

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Table of Contents

	Page
Table of Contents	2
A. Description	3
B. Sample timeline	3
Legends	4

Legend by country:

HOAL Austria Crop 1 (wheat)
HOAL Austria Crop 2 (corn)
HOAL Portugal Crop 1 and 2
HOAL Czech Republic Crop 1 and 2
HOAL Estonia Crop 1 and 2
Farm Great Britain
WWTP Ireland

Legend by Sample Compartment:

	Sample from:
P	Pig farm
M	Manure
S	Soil
Fs	Forest
Ms	Meadow
C	Crop
D	Field drainage
R	River water
Dw	Drinking water
G	Ground water
Fe	Feed
Fa	Farmers
WTP	Wastewater treatment plant
Ww	Wild Animals